

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF ONLINE EDUCATION OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS UNDER STATE BOARD SYLLABUS

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Abstract: *The purpose of this study was to conduct a survey regarding students' interest and satisfaction related to online classes during the pandemic period of COVID-19. Delivery of classes through online medium has been a recent modification brought by the education system in all over India in the current pandemic situation. Thus, this survey describes high school students under board syllabus' interest and perceptions with regard to taking online classes that have been made mandatory in the pandemic situation and the data were collected from 50 respondents by the children's of high school under state board syllabus in Bengaluru.*

Keywords : COVID-19, High school, Mental health, Online classes, Students interest, State board.

Introduction

Coronavirus is a disease, which is spreading very fast amongst the human beings. The influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on the education system leads to schools and colleges' widespread closures worldwide. On March 24th, India declared a country wide lockdown of schools and colleges for preventing the transmission of the coronavirus amongst the students. School closures in response to the COVID-19 have affecting several issues to education. As a versatile platform for learning and teaching processes, the E-learning framework has been increasingly used. E-learning is defined as a new platform of online learning based on information technology. In contrast to online classes, students are facing many problems to attend the classes. Only by the analysing students' problems the answer be sought. The data were collected by the 50 respondents by the high school students under state board syllabus.

Statement of problem

Nowadays, Online education is very difficult on the students. It's very difficult to listen the in classes in the online because the internet connection is very low, network error happens in sometimes then students are not interested to listen the classes and mind divert to some other

work.

Importance of the study

This is an analysis on High school children preference towards online education Under state board syllabus. An attempt has been made by the research to know the preference, understanding, and satisfaction etc.

Objective of the study

- To analyses the analysis and difficulties of online education
- To know the impact of online education on the students mental health

Research Methodology

For this study, the students difficulties about online education data has been collected. The students survey had a three sections of socio economic questionnaires and 18 questionnaire regarding students perception about attending online classes and the performance . The students were asked to tell what according to them were the positive and negative aspects of online teaching and what were the applications usually used by them to take online classes. Response choices consisted of pre-defined options of yes or no , easy or difficult and other options . The data was collected by the 50 respondents of high school students under state board syllabus where 50 students have completed the entire questionnaires prepared. The data was shared with respondents by the hard copies.

Findings and Result

Socio- economic characteristics may influence the main purpose of the study was to gather evaluate feedback from the high school students on their experience about online mode of teaching.

Difficulties of online education on High school children

There are many difficulties faced by the high school students for attending the online classes without reliable internet access and technology struggle to participate in digital learning and understanding capacity of students in online is very low.

Table 1: Difficulties of online education

Difficulties	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	23	46
No	27	54
Total	50	100

Table 1 studies about the difficulties faced by online education. 46% of students have faced difficulties from the online education and 54% of students have not faced any difficulties from online education.

Understanding lessons through the online classes

Online education and offline education is very different from one another and when it comes to understanding capacity of children's through online is very different and lack of concentration and interest.

Table 2: Understanding lessons through online classes

Understanding ability	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	9	18
No	41	82
Total	50	100

Table 2 shows that 18% of students are understanding lessons through online classes and 82% of students are not able to understand the lessons through online classes.

About online classes

Teaching has gone online because of COVID-19. Online classes has advantages and as well as disadvantages to students and teachers to understand the lessons and saving time and money for travelling.

Table 3: About online classes

About online classes	No of respondents	Percentage
Easy	9	18%
Difficult	41	82%
Total	50	100%

Table 3 shows that 18% of students feel online education is easy to understand and access and 82% of students are feeling difficulty from the online education.

Difficulties faced by students to connect to the internet

Many high school students have faced lot of problems during the pandemic situation because of network problems, Mobile recharge (financial problems), separate space to attend the online classes without any disturbance.

Table 4: Difficulties to connect to the internet

Difficulties to connect	No of respondents	Percentage
Easy	13	26
Difficult	37	74
Total	50	100

Table 4 shows that 26% of students are not facing any difficulties to attend the online classes through internet and 74% of students are facing difficulty to attend the online classes through internet.

Devices used to attend the online classes

This is the most vital thing to have at your place from where you wish to attend the online classes. Without wifi, you won't be able to connect with the classes and won't be able to acquire the knowledge.

Table 5: Devices used to attend the online classes

Devices	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Mobile Phone	36	72%
Laptop	9	18%
Tablet	5	10%
Desktop	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Table 5 shows that 72% of students use mobile phones to attend the online classes and 18% of students use laptop to attend the online classes and 10% of students use tablet to attend the online classes and no one uses the desktop to attend the online classes.

Childers satisfaction with the way of teaching

Not every student is happy with the way of teaching by their teachers. High school students have there own way of learning but online learning have been very difficult them to understand and concentrate for both students and teachers have there own way of teaching style.

Table 6:Childrens satisfaction with the way of teaching

Satisfaction of teaching	No of respondents	Percentage
More than usual	6	12
As usual	24	48
Less than usual	16	32

Not at all	4	8
Total	50	100

Table 6 studies about the students satisfaction with the way of teaching of teachers in online classes. 12% of students said more than usual and 48% of students said as usual and 32% of students said less than usual and 8% of students are not satisfied with the way of teaching in online classes.

Effectiveness of online learning

Online classes are more effective, because many students learn fast in the offline classes and many few students learn fast in online classes. students are not listening the classes they are roaming around school and wasting time

Table 7: Effectiveness of online learning

Effectiveness of online	No of respondents	Percentage
Extremely effective	2	4
Very effective	16	32
Moderate	21	42
Slightly effective	6	12
Not at all effective	5	10
Total	50	100

Table 7 studies about the effectiveness of the online learning been for students. 4% of students have said it is extremely effective and 32% of students have said it is very effective and 42% of students have said it is moderate and 12% of students said slightly effective and 10% of students said it is not at all effective.

Mental illness by online education

Online education is a very dangerous for small kids and children's for attending the online classes continuously because many students get into mental health issues and many other problems which students cannot even know about what mental health is about.

Table 8 : Mental illness by online education

Mental illness	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	30	60
No	20	40
Total	50	100

Table 8 shows that 60% of students have faced mental health issues by online classes and 40% of students have not faced any mental health issues by online classes.

Emotional / Behavioral disorders

Emotional disturbances can affect students and teachers by attending the online classes and having emotionally stable and they are socially and it can also have many disorders about emotional and Behavioural disorders.

Table: 9 Emotional / Behavioral disorders

Emotional/Behavioral disorders	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	29	58
No	21	42
Total	50	100

Table 9 shows that 58% of students faced emotional or behavioral health issues due to online classes and 42% of students have not faced any emotional or behavioral health issues due to online classes.

Feeling outburst for not meeting friends and teachers physically

During COVID-19, the online education has made physically not being able to meet there friends and teachers and not having any direct contact that causes loneliness and outburst for every students and teachers.

Table 10: Feeling outburst for not meeting friends and teachers physically

Outburst to meet physically	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	25	50
No	25	50
Total	50	100

Table 10 studies about students feeling outburst for being not able to meet their friends and teachers physically. 50% of students have felt outburst for being not able to meet friends and teachers physically and remaining 50% of students have not felt outburst for being not able to meet their friends and teachers physically.

Teachers helping students to overcome the mental illness

Each and every student needs their teachers' help during offline as well as online learning. Teachers should help the students to overcome from mental illness by continuously listening to online classes and not having any activity hour feels boredom and frustrated that cause mental health issues.

Table 11: Teachers helping students to overcome the mental illness

Teachers helping	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	16	32
No	34	68
Total	50	100

Table 11 shows that 32% of students getting help from teachers to overcome from the mental illness and 68% of students are not getting any help from teachers to overcome from the mental illness.

Parents helping to overcoming the mental illness

Every parent have to see to it that what problem children's are struggling from support them to overcome from mental illness. Every parent have to solve there problems about online education which cannot be understood easily by high school students.

Table 12 : Parents helping to overcoming the mental illness

Parents helping	No of respondents	Percentage
Yes	20	40
No	30	60
Total	50	100

Table 12 shows that 40% of students are getting help from parents to overcome from mental illness and remaining 60% of students are not getting any help from parents to overcome from mental illness.

Feelings during the online classes

Students feel different kinds of feelings during the online classes like low mood to continuously listen to online classes, Boredom and fear, frustrated of watching continuously to screen and every students feel various of feelings by the online learning.

Table 13: Feelings during the online classes

Feelings of online classes	No of respondents	Percentage
Low mood	24	48
Boredom and fear	11	22
Frustrated	11	22
Interesting	04	8
Total	50	100

Table 13 studies about the feelings during the online classes. 48% of students feel low mood during online classes and 22% of students feel boredom and fear and 12% of students feel frustrated during online classes and 8% of students feel interesting during the online classes.

Kinds of Mental illness

Mental illness are treatable and students have mood swings, anxiety and Irritability due to the online education.

Table 14: Kinds of Mental illness

Kinds of mental illness	No of respondents	Percentage
Irritability and mood swings	20	40
Anxiety and low mood	17	34
Anger and outburst	09	18
No, not faced	04	8
Total	50	100

Table 14 studies about the kinds of mental health issues that students are facing during the online classes. 40% of students feel irritability and mood swings and 34% of students feel anxiety and low mood and 18% of students feel anger and outburst and 8% of students have not faced any of the mental health issues by the online classes.

Symptoms of Mental illness

Mental illness are thinking abilities, overthinking, sadness, feeling lonely and powerless. Students are facing many symptoms of mental health issues about even they couldn't know about it that they are suffering from mental health issues.

Table 15: Symptoms of Mental illness

Symptoms	No of respondents	Percentage
Sadness, feeling of being overwhelmed	17	34
Changes in sleeping habits and eating	15	30
Feelings of hopeless and powerless	16	32
No, I have not faced	02	4
Total	50	100

Table 15 studies about the symptoms of mental health faced by students during online education. 34% of students faced sadness, feeling of being overwhelmed and 30% of students faced changes in there sleeping habits and eating routines and 32% of students faced powerless and hopeless and 4% of students have not faced any of the symptoms. This shows 96% of students have faced various kinds of mental health and only 4% of students not faced any of the symptoms by the online education.

Results

The survey was done to get an understanding of the experience and perception of students about the recently introduced online mode of teaching. The students reported that they preferred to classroom teaching method more than online teaching mode as per the survey done. As per the data analysis 50 students of high school preferred to traditional learning.

Discussion

The result of this study discuss that traditional learning was positively in terms of activities done in traditional classroom , interaction between students and teachers , satisfaction of understanding the lessons and overall quality . Even though the online classes were convenient in term of saving time technical support was found to be an important factor critical to determining dissatisfied with online classes. The students showed dissatisfaction towards online classes when instructors were unavailable to provide technical support. Hence, this survey shows most of the students from high school students under state board syllabus have many problems like mental health issues and financial problems and so on.

Conclusion

During pandemic situation students difficulties and teachers learning habits are discussed here and many difficulties are not recognised and many have so many problems about the online education system to involve there life and get adjusted to it and try to understand the lessons through online classes and the data have been collected from the 50 students about the online education classes and founded there difficulties about the online education classes.

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